

Effectiveness of educational methods of lectures and lectures with leaflet regarding husband's knowledge about postpartum care at Naval Central hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya

Qusnul Khotimah ¹, Astika Gita Ningrum ^{1,*}, Samsriyaningsih Handayani ² and Ivon Diah Wittiarika ¹

¹ *Midwifery Study Program Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia.*

² *Department of Public Health and Preventive Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia.*

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Abstract

Introduction: The postpartum period is critical in the survival of the mother and newborn. Most maternal and newborn deaths occur within the first month after delivery. Mothers and newborns need health care during this period to avoid the risk of illness and death. The importance of the husband's contribution to postpartum care is greatly influenced by the husband's knowledge about postpartum care.

Objective: This research aims to determine the effectiveness of providing education through lecture and lecture methods with leaflets to increase husbands' knowledge about postpartum care.

Method: This research is a type of quasi-experimental research. The research design uses a pre-posttest one-group design with questions about the husband's knowledge about the time of delivery. Sampling techniques are consecutive sampling, with 15 people in the lecture group and 15 people in the lecture group with leaflets. Data is collected using questionnaires. Statistical tests are used using the Wilcoxon signed test and Mann Whitney test.

Result: A significant majority (65.7%) of the sampled toddlers were diagnosed. The research results showed that the average knowledge of respondents about postpartum care before being given health education using leaflet lectures was 61.4, and after being given health education was 74.2. Meanwhile, the results of the lecture method with leaflets showed that the average knowledge of respondents about early marriage before being given education was 61.2, and after education, using the lecture method with leaflets increased to 78.6. By testing Mann Whitney, the significance obtained was $0.023 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the lecture method and lecture method with leaflet.

Conclusion: Lecture education using leaflets is more effective than the lecture method in increasing husbands' knowledge about postpartum care at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya.

Keywords: Postpartum period; Lectures; Leaflets; Maternal Health.

1. Introduction

The postpartum period is a critical period in the survival of the mother and newborn. Most maternal and newborn deaths occur in the first month after delivery; for this reason, postnatal services are needed involving mothers, husbands and families in maintaining the health of postpartum mothers and newborns (1). Support from the husband and family is essential during the initial adaptation to motherhood. Husband support is a highly effective means of alleviating

* Corresponding author: Astika Gita Ningrum

anxiety during pregnancy, reducing pain during childbirth, and mitigating feelings of postpartum depression in wives(2).

The husband's lack of support for the mother during the postpartum period makes the mother feel neglected and stressed, making the mother feel depressed and giving rise to a negative attitude, which leads to bad behaviour, for example, not wanting to eat and being reluctant to check back with health workers, which can hurt their health (3).

Considering the importance of monitoring the postpartum period, it will be dangerous for mothers if they do not carry out re-controls or postpartum visits because up to now, the maternal mortality rate in the postpartum period is still high. The global MMR data for 2020 is 223 per 100,000 live births, while the data for 2022 is around 183 per 100 thousand live births, where this figure is still far from achieving the global SDGs, namely 70 per 100 thousand live births (WHO, 2023), whereas Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) survey in ASEAN namely 235 per 100,000 live births(4). In the latest 2020 survey by the Central Statistics Agency, the maternal mortality rate in Indonesia was 189 per 100,000 live births (5). Based on data from the Sampling Registration System (SRS) in 2018, around 76% of maternal deaths occurred in the labour and postpartum phase, with a proportion of 24% occurring during pregnancy, 36% during childbirth, and 40% during postpartum. Based on the cause, the majority of maternal deaths in 2020 were caused by bleeding (more than 1,330 deaths), high blood pressure during pregnancy (more than 1,110 deaths), and circulatory disorders (230 deaths).

The still high maternal mortality rate during the postpartum period can be anticipated with optimal postpartum care, including by conducting return visits during the postpartum period to detect the mother's condition during the postpartum period(7). Postpartum care can be carried out by the postpartum mother and her family with the assistance of health workers until the mother's condition returns to normal before pregnancy (8). For this reason, it is necessary to strengthen knowledge of postpartum care among mothers and families so that mothers receive full support during the postpartum period.

The husband's knowledge about the danger signs during the postpartum period has been proven to change the husband's behaviour by providing positive support for care during the postpartum period (9). Several factors influence knowledge: education, age, employment, information, experience, environment, society, economy, culture, and health education carried out by health workers during pregnancy and after giving birth (10). Health education can be obtained from various sources. One study on health education for patients' husbands found that health education using audiovisual media to support husbands during pregnancy was classified as effective(11). There is also research that shows that Health Education Methods Brainstorming and Buzz Group can increase the knowledge of pregnant women's husbands about the dangerous signs of pregnancy, childbirth and postpartum(12).

Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya, one of the leading referral hospitals in Surabaya, has a relatively high number of births. Data obtained from Naval Central Hospital Surabaya in 2022 showed 588 postpartum mothers, with a history of standard delivery of 166 patients and a history of delivery by SC of 422 patients (Medical Records of Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya 2021. If in percentage, then the number of SC at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya is relatively high, around 70% of the total postpartum mothers. Most postpartum mothers' companions at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya are husbands. Considering the importance of postpartum patient care needs, researchers are interested in increasing husbands' knowledge about postpartum care. To effectively support mothers through the postpartum period and prevent complications, one effort to increase husbands' knowledge is to provide education regarding postpartum care.

Researchers will utilize two methods to provide education: lectures and lecture leaflets. Lectures are the most accessible and cost-effective educational tools that can be conducted in various settings. Additionally, the lecture method enables direct interaction between researchers and respondents, fostering immediate reciprocal engagement. Including leaflet media in this research aims to augment the educational process, as leaflets are portable and can be accessed and reviewed conveniently from any location.

Based on this description, researchers want to research the effectiveness of providing education through methods such as lectures and lectures with Leaflet to increase husbands' knowledge about postpartum care at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya. This research aims to compare the educational effectiveness of lecture and lecture methods with love on husband's knowledge about postpartum care at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya.

2. Material and methods

This research is a type of quasi-experimental quantitative research (quasi-experimental research). The quasi-experimental design has an experimental class and a control class. The control class in this research is lecture education, and the experimental class is lecture education class with Leaflet.

The research design uses a pre-posttest intervention with the control group. This research was conducted to see the effect of giving lectures and lectures with Leaflets regarding postpartum care for husbands of postpartum mothers at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya. The research was conducted by treating one control group in the form of counselling with lectures and one experimental group in the form of counselling with lectures and giving Leaflets.

The study's population was the husbands of postpartum mothers being treated in room E at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya, who filled out and returned the questionnaire during the research, was willing to attend the researcher's education and met the inclusion criteria.

The research sample here is the husband of a postpartum mother who is being treated in room E at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya is willing to complete and return the questionnaire and meet the inclusion criteria for both regular and natural births, Caesar, with a sample size of 30 people. The sampling technique in this research is a consecutive sample.

This research was conducted in Room E Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya, which will be held from October 2023 to March 2024. The independent variables in this research are lectures and lectures with Leaflet about postpartum care, while the dependent variable is knowledge.

The measuring tool or instrument in this research is a questionnaire. The questionnaire was adapted from the 2024 Indonesian Ministry of Health layout regarding postpartum care. It has been tested for validity with SPSS 25 and reliability with a formula Cronbach Alpha (> 0.05).

Data processing in this study used univariate and bivariate analysis to determine the effectiveness of the educational methods provided. Before bivariate analysis was carried out, a data normality test was carried out. Because the data is not normally distributed, the Wilcoxon signed test and Uji Mann Whitney are used. Next, a Ngain score test was carried out to determine the comparison of effectiveness between the two methods used.

3. Result

3.1. Presentation of General Characteristics and Data

The general data in the research is a research description of the characteristics of the respondents, namely the husbands of postpartum mothers at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya. The number of respondents was 30, and they had filled out the questionnaire. The following are the characteristics of the respondents in this study:

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents

variable	Lectures Group		Lectures with Leaflets Group	
	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)
Age	1	6,66	0	0
< 20 y.o	12	80	9	60
20-35 y.o	2	13,33	6	40
>35 y.o				
Total	15	100	15	100
Education Background				
Elementary School	0	0	1	6,6
Junior High School	2	13,3	2	13,3

Senior High School DIPLOMA/ Bachelor		10	66.6	12	80
		3	20	0	0
Total		15	100	15	100
Occupation Does not work Private Civil servant		0	0	0	0
		14	93.3	11	73.3
		1	6.6	4	26.6
Total		15	100	15	100

From Table 1 above, the distribution of the 30 research respondents consists of various characteristics, where the majority of respondents are aged 20-35 years, namely 80% of lecture respondents and 60% of lecture respondents with leaflets. Regarding education, it is known that most respondents were high school graduates, namely 66.6% of lecture respondents and 80% of lecture respondents with leaflets. In the work variable, most respondents work in the private sector, amounting to 93.3% of lecture respondents and 73.3% of lecture respondents with Leaflet; the rest work as Civil servants.

3.2. Bivariate Analysis

Table 2 Data normality test

	Lectures			Lecture with leaflets		
	N	%	Sig.	N	100	Sig.
pre_test	15	100	0.693	15	100	0.048
post_test	15	100	0.046	15	100	0.070

*Shapiro Wilk's Test

Based on Table 2 above, it can be concluded that neither data is normally distributed.

Table 3 Analysis of husband's knowledge before and after lecture education

Variable	N	%	Mean Ranks	P value
Pre-test	15	100	67.13	0.002
Posttest	15	100	76.93	

*Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test

Based on Table 3 above, the sig value is obtained. (2-tailed) of $0.009 < 0.05$. Based on these results, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the knowledge results before being given education and after receiving lecture education. This is because the lecture method is effective in increasing respondents' knowledge.

Table 4 Analysis of Husband's Knowledge Before and After Educational Lectures with Leaflets

Variable	N	%	Mean Ranks	P value
Pre-test	15	100	10.887	0.001
Posttest	15	100	14.373	

*Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test

Based on Table 4 above, the sig value is obtained. (2-tailed) of $0.001 < 0.05$. Based on these results, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the knowledge results before being given education and after receiving educational lectures with leaflets.

Table 4 Analysis of the educational effectiveness of lecture and lecture methods with Leaflet

Enhancement Knowledge	N	Mean Rank	P value
Lectures	15	11.87	0.023
Lectures with leaflets	15	19.13	

*Uji Mann Whitney

Based on the statistical test output above, the value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) of $0.023 < 0.05$. So, there is a difference between lecture method education and lecture method education leaflet.

Table 6 N-Gain Test Results for educational lectures

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Ngain_score1	15	-0.41	69	0.2548	0.33977

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that the average (mean) N-Gain score knowledge in the lecture class gained a value mean of 0.25. So, based on the scale, N-Gain is included in the low effectiveness category.

Table 7 Results of the N gain test of lecture education with Leaflet.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Ngain_score1	15	-0.6	1.00	0.5158	0.29021

Based on Table 7, the average (mean) N-Gain score for the learning result in the lecture class was 0.51. So, it can be concluded that, based on categories, the N-Gain score is included in the medium effectiveness category. From the test results of the N-Gain score Above, it can be concluded that the lecture education method uses Leaflet more effectively than other methods.

4. Discussion

4.1. Respondent Characteristics

Respondents who participated in the research came from the husbands of postpartum mothers treated at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya. There were 30 people in Ramelan Surabaya, consisting of 15 in the control group and 15 in the experimental group. Based on research results, the majority of husbands are in the 20-35 years old range at 66%. The majority of respondents' education, 73.3%, was high school graduates. Most respondents' jobs, 83.3%, were in the private sector.

Education is closely related to knowledge. Education is a basic human need and significant for self-development. The higher the level of education, the easier it is to obtain and expand knowledge. (13).

It is also possible for all respondents who are workers to gain much knowledge from their work environment; this may be due to the possibility of gaining knowledge and experience that can be obtained indirectly or directly through the work environment (14).

Apart from the above, the age factor of the respondents, most of whom are of productive age, could be a factor in the ease with which respondents receive education. This is by Notoadmodjo's statement, namely that as a person gets older, the person's memory will also increase. A person's age will influence the increase in knowledge they have (13).

4.2. Husband's knowledge about postpartum care before and after lecture education.

After health education in the form of lectures was carried out in the control group, it was seen that there was a significant difference in the respondents' knowledge before and after lecture education was carried out through the Wilcoxon signed test. The significance value obtained was $0.002 < 0.05$ which shows a significant difference between the score before and after education, which means that health education uses the lecture method effectively to increase respondents' knowledge regarding postpartum care. This aligns with Lulu Yunita's research (15), which shows that health education lectures influence increasing mothers' knowledge in handling diarrhea in children at home.

The lecture method is the most common consultation method. This lecture method is very effective for all target groups, both those with high and low levels of education(16). Lectures are the process of transferring information from the teacher to the learning target. The teaching process has three essential elements: the teacher, the material and the learning targets. Lectures are used for learning targets that have selective attention, limited scope of attention, and require categorical and systematic information (10). This method is practical and efficient for teaching that requires much material and has many students. The advantage of the lecture method is that it is easy and cheap.

4.3. Husband's knowledge about postpartum care before and after educational lectures and Leaflets

After carrying out health education in the form of a lecture method with Leaflet in the experimental group, it was seen that there was an increase in good knowledge from 61.2 to 78.6. Test results Wilcoxon signed test shows a significant value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$), which shows that there is a significant difference between the score before education and the score after education, which means that health education uses the lecture method with Leaflet effective in increasing respondents' knowledge regarding postpartum care. In the previous method, the effectiveness of the lecture method was discussed. In the following method, education is still given using the lecture method but is added by giving a Leaflet about postpartum care. This method can obtain a higher average value compared to the lecture method.

This increase in knowledge is likely due to the methods and tools used. The method used in this guide is lectures supported by tools such as lecture group leaflets with leaflets. Form leaflets that are short, concise, exciting and clear can also increase respondents' interest in reading them. This research indicates that adding methods leaflets in lectures effectively increases respondents' knowledge. This is in line with other research conducted by Fera Meliyanti regarding the effectiveness of using the lecture method with Leaflet towards increasing the knowledge of class VIII teenagers about HIV/AIDS at SMP Negeri 2 Ogan Komering Ulu, where the results of the research showed that the lecture method using Leaflet quite effective in increasing students' knowledge about HIV/AIDS(17).

4.4. Effectiveness of Providing Education Through Lecture and Lecture Methods with Leaflet Regarding Changes in Husbands' Knowledge About Postpartum Care.

Providing information on lecture and lecture methods with Leaflets effectively increased respondents' knowledge. However, the average (mean) post-test score in the lecture group was 74.2, and in the lecture group with the leaflet, it was 78.6. Then, the lecture method with Leaflet is more effective in increasing respondents' knowledge; this is by the concept of knowledge, where most human knowledge is obtained through the eyes and ears (18). The more senses are used to receive knowledge, the more and clearer the knowledge will be (10). In this case, the education method is lectures and media leaflets. The aim is to mobilize as many senses as possible to make it easier for respondents to understand.

After the respondent received information on the lecture method, the respondent came to know and understand postpartum care so that he could apply the material he received; then, the respondent could explain the material provided even though it was still not perfect; after that, an evaluation was carried out using a questionnaire to determine the respondent's knowledge about postpartum care. Providing information using lectures is quite suitable for increasing knowledge, but the lecture method using Leaflet has proven to be more effective because one of the weaknesses of the lecture method is that it makes respondents less creative; there may be learning material that respondents have not been able to absorb optimally. Also, teachers need help knowing how much material respondents can absorb; the lecture method is more about verbalism and less stimulating. To cover the shortcomings of the lecture method, increasing knowledge is strengthened by using leaflets; according to Edgar Dale's cone theory, the level of understanding achieved in reading is 10%, while in listening activities. The level of understanding is 20% (19). Meanwhile, according to Ahmad Rosidi, the more something is seen, heard, said and done, the easier it is for us to learn something; we remember an average of 20% of what we read and 30% of what we hear (20).

From the results of the research carried out, the author thinks that lecture groups and lectures with Leaflets both experienced an increase in knowledge, but using the lecture method leaflet proved to be more effective; this can be seen

from the highest mean knowledge in the lecture group with Leaflet because it uses more than one sense, namely listening and reading Leaflet so that the information can be better understood. The lecture method using media leaflets can increase knowledge because this method requires someone to learn something well using more than one sense, namely sight and hearing. This is by Edgar Dale's vision of the cone of experience, which was the first attempt to provide a reason or basis for the relationship between learning theory and audiovisual communication, that what we see and hear adds up to 30% of the information (Dale, 1946). The more senses are used to receive information, the more affluent and clearer the understanding or knowledge(13).

5. Conclusion

Based on the analysis and discussion of the effectiveness of education delivery methods at Naval Central Hospital dr. Ramelan Surabaya in enhancing husbands' understanding of postpartum care, several conclusions can be drawn. Firstly, both the educational lecture with Leaflet and the lecture method alone led to a significant increase in husbands' knowledge about postpartum care. However, it was found that providing education through verbal presentations accompanied by leaflets was more effective than using the lecture method alone. Moreover, combining the lecture method with leaflets resulted in even greater efficacy in enhancing husbands' knowledge about postpartum care compared to using the lecture method alone.

Moving forward, it is recommended to encourage the implementation of educational sessions that integrate verbal presentations with leaflet distribution. This approach can optimize the effectiveness of postpartum care education for husbands. Furthermore, future research endeavors could explore additional methods of delivering postpartum care education to husbands, taking into consideration diverse learning preferences and accessibility. Such efforts would contribute to further enhancing the effectiveness and inclusivity of postpartum care education initiatives.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest.

Statement of Ethical Approval

Ethical clearance was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Soewandhie Regional Hospital, Surabaya, East Java, Indonesia Number2/EC/KEP/2024 on 3 January 2024.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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